

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004480.

Project Acronym:	AI4PublicPolicy
Project Title:	Automated, Transparent Citizen-Centric Public Policy Making based on Trusted Artificial Intelligence
Project Number:	101004480
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme DT-GOVERNANCE-12-2019-2020 Pilot on using the European cloud infrastructure for public administrations
Type of Action:	IA - Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	March 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D6.9 Energy Management Policies Pilot V1

(Version 1.0, 28/12/2022)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©AI4PublicPolicy Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Deliverable:	D6.9 – Energy Management Policies Pilot V1	
Work Package:	WP6 – Use Cases and Pilots Integration, Validation and Evaluation	
Due Date:	30/11/2022	
Submission Date:	28/12/2022	
Lead Beneficiary:	LIS	
Version:	1.0	
Status:	Final version	
Author name(s):	Sara Freitas (LIS)	
Reviewer(s):	Tiago Teixeira (UNP)	Vagia Kalliontzi (NOVO)
Keywords:	implementation, integration, deployment, policies, user stories, datasets, KPIs, VPME, stakeholders, citizens	
Nature:	<input type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

The **AI4PublicPolicy** Consortium consists of:

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country	Project entry date	Project exit date
1	GFT ITALIA SRL	GFT	Italy		
2	STICHTING EGI	EGI	Netherlands		
3	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT	INTRA	Luxembourg		
4	SIA SPA	SIA	Italy		13/7/2022
5	NOVOVILLE LIMITED	NOVO	United Kingdom		
6	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	UNP	Portugal		
7	VILABS (CY) LTD	VIL	Cyprus		
8	ARTHUR'S LEGAL BV	ALBV	Netherlands		
9	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain		
10	DIMOS ATHINAION EPICHEIRISI MICHANOGRAFISIS	DAEM	Greece		
11	COMUNE DI GENOVA	CDG	Italy		
12	LEFKOSIA MUNICIPALITY	NIC	Cyprus		
13	LISBOA E-NOVA - AGENCIA DE ENERGIA E AMBIENTE DE LISBOA	LIS	Portugal		
14	MESTSKA CAST PRAHA 9	PRA	Czechia		13/08/2021
15	REPORTBRAIN LIMITED	RB	UK	01/06/2021	
16	BURGAS MUNICIPALITY	BURGAS	Bulgaria	22/07/2021	
17	EKSO SRL	EKSO	Italy	05/07/2021	
18	TECNE SOCIETA A RESPONSABILITA LIMITATA	TECNE	Italy	01/02/2022	

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	01/04/2022	Vagia Kalliontzi (NOVO)	Table of Contents
0.2	08/04/2022	Vagia Kalliontzi (NOVO)	First draft
0.3	20/11/2022	Sara Freitas (LIS)	Contribution to all sections
0.4	22/12/2022	ALL PARTNERS	Implementation template revised
0.5	23/12/2022	Sara Freitas (LIS)	Full version to be reviewed
1.0	28/12/2022	Sara Freitas (LIS)	Final version to be submitted

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	5
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	5
Abbreviations	6
Executive summary.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project.....	8
1.2 Description of WP6.....	9
1.3 Purpose and scope of the document	9
1.4 Structure of the document	9
2 Pilot policies.....	10
2.1 Policy #1 - Photovoltaic (PV) systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon.....	10
2.1.1 User stories	10
2.1.2 Description.....	10
2.1.3 Objective.....	11
2.1.4 Key Policy Indicators (KPI)	11
2.2 Policy Datasets.....	12
3 New Policy Making Process Definition	15
4 Feedback from Users/Stakeholders	18
4.1 Feedback Collection Plan and Methods.....	18
5 Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use	20
5.1 Engagement plan and status	20
5.2 Training plan and status	21

List of Figures

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach.....	8
Figure 2. Definition of Policy #1 in the VPME	12
Figure 3. Datasets defined in the VPME	14
Figure 4. Schematic of the energy management policy making process based on VPME.....	15
Figure 5. List of users of the Pilot group in the VO.	16
Figure 6. Preliminary feedback survey created in the VPME.....	18

List of Tables

Table 1. List of User Stories explored in Policy #1.	10
Table 2. KPI related to Policy #1.....	11
Table 3. Datasets associated to Policy #1.....	12
Table 4. Training Plan and Status (LIS)	21

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
KPI	Key Policy Indicator
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the implementation steps of the Energy Management Policies pilot located in Lisbon, Portugal. The first policy has been defined and concerns the monitoring of the solar photovoltaic panels installed in the city based on aerial images that allow for the identification of existing systems, pinpoint their locations, and estimate their sizes and installed power (Section 2). Many new policies can stem from this one in the future to inform the concretization of Lisbon's solar energy goals.

Main steps in the implementation of this Pilot (Section 3) encompass: a) the systematization of data in relation to the policies with greater implementation potential, their cataloguing and curation; b) policy testing and evaluation; and c) improvement of policies and continuous co-creation with the stakeholders' ecosystem. A user/stakeholder feedback collection plan (Section 4) and training plans (Section 5) have been described.

This document is V1 of the result of Task 6.5 so far, and later in the project V2 of this deliverable will be submitted with all the details on the implementation of the Energy Management Policies pilot.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realisation of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organisation transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach.

1.2 Description of WP6

The WP6 is the pilot's work-package that will be devoted to deploying, operating, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active engagement of the public authorities of the consortium.

The main objectives are as follow:

- Undertake preparatory activities at the five (5) pilot sites towards their readiness for the pilot operations.
- Customise and deploy the AI4PublicPolicy outcomes in-line with the requirements and needs of the 5 pilot sites.
- Operate and validate the AI4PublicPolicy platform in different use cases and contexts in the 5 pilot sites.
- Evaluate the pilot systems from a technical and a business perspective.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable will be devoted to the integration, deployment and operation of the project's pilot systems and policies. The work will involve tailoring and customization of the AI4PublicPolicy platform and tools to the needs of the pilot, including the implementation of pilot specific data models and features, as well as connectors to the data sources of the pilot.

The operation of the system will engage relevant stakeholders, including citizens, experts, and businesses. The task will continually improve the implementation and operation of the pilot systems and policies based on feedback from user studies and focus groups (as described in Task 2.6).

1.4 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following sections:

- **Section 1: Introduction** – This section presents an introduction to the project, the W6, the purpose and scope of the current document as well as its structure.
- **Section 2: Pilot policies** – contains all the details (policy name, user story, description, objective and KPIs) regarding the pilot policies that will be deployed for the pilot. In addition, the policy datasets are fully described. Finally, a demonstration of the definition of the policies and datasets with the usage of the Policy and Data Management Component is provided.
- **Section 3: New Policy Making Process Definition** – defines the new organisation processes that need to be in place in order to implement the new pilot policies. Moreover, it contains all details on how the various components of the VPME will be incorporated in the process and how the VPME will be used in the new policy making process; A screenshot of the single Virtual Organisation is provided.
- **Section 4: Feedback from Users/Stakeholders** – describes the methodologies that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders; Screenshots from surveys created with the Policy Evaluation toolkit will be shown.
- **Section 5: Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use** – demonstrates the methodologies that will be followed to engage stakeholders in the internal implementation and usage of the VPME. Furthermore, pilots also describe the steps needed to be taken in order to train the stakeholders.

2 Pilot policies

2.1 Policy #1 - Photovoltaic (PV) systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon

All the details of the first policy defined are reported in this section, such as the co-created User Stories that helped to shape and refine the policy, its description and goals, and the key indicators that will allow for its monitoring.

2.1.1 User stories

As per Section 4.6 of *D2.1 – Use case scenarios definition and design*, the User Stories that are related to this Policy are:

Table 1. List of User Stories explored in Policy #1.

User Stories ID	As a «type of user», ... Identify the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.	... I want «some goal» ... Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.	... so that «some reason». Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.
US38	City officer/Energy agency	To identify and locate the PV systems installed in the city as well as to know their areas	To understand about the city energy production performance; be able to deduce installed capacity; and infer about the city's PV adoption curve through time
US39	City officer/Energy agency/Building(s) owner(s)	To know about the city's potential PV energy production	To be able to monitor PV energy production potential and draw scenarios elucidating about the achievement of the city's defined goals and targets for 2030
US41	City officer/Energy agency	Analyse PV datasets from different data sources (e.g. orthophotomaps, satellite images, and others available)	To have a wider range of datasets and that can help me analyse the potential of renewables (PV)
US42	Building(s) owner(s) and citizens	To know the potential PV energy production of the building(s) owner(s) and citizens	To provide estimates about potential cost savings

2.1.2 Description

The Lisbon Solar City strategy is part of Lisbon's Climate Action Plan for 2030, contributing to the city's decarbonisation goals with a 103 MW installed photovoltaic (PV) capacity target by 2030. Given that currently the city has only 8 MW installed PV capacity, the Action Plan develops along two major vectors – municipal and private end-use sectors.

Due to the unavailability of up-to-date and detailed information about Lisbon's existing solar energy systems, the city is unable to track its progress in relation to its 2030 goals. Thus, this policy aims at establishing a data-based decision making for targeted implementation of PV in the city buildings.

Although there are two major types of solar technology for energy production – the Photovoltaic for electricity production and the Solar Thermal (ST) for heating water – the focus of this policy is on PV, since it is the most efficient solar technology under Lisbon's typical weather and more suited to leverage the electrification of the energy supply system.

2.1.3 Objective

To monitor the yearly achieved PV installed capacity based on the identification of existing systems, their locations, sizes and, when possible, further characterization. The solar installations detected by the AI algorithm will be input to a map to be made publicly available - an update to the existing but very incomplete map currently available in the city's Solis platform¹.

2.1.4 Key Policy Indicators (KPI)

One set of indicators were defined to track the evolution of solar installations in the city, which will help to monitor and inform the implementation of the city's solar-related plans and the creation of tailored support mechanisms.

Table 2. KPI related to Policy #1.

KPI	KPI Description
Installed capacity (MWp)	City and parish scale PV peak power (in the year corresponding to the available aerial images)
% of achievement of 2030 goal (103 MWp)	How close/far the city is from reaching this Climate Action goal
Installed capacity vs theoretical potential	How much capacity is currently installed in the city (and per parish) comparing to the maximum theoretical potential
Number of PV installations	Number of detected installations existing in the city (and in each parish)
Number of PV panels	Estimated amount of PV panels in each detected installation, as well the total existing in the city
Number of other solar installations (ST)	Number of detected ST installations existing in the city (and in each parish)

This first set of KPI might be complemented in the future through users' and stakeholders' feedback, further explained in section 4. As such, for this particular policy, the expected feedback-based KPI could be:

- # accesses/interactions with the public map
- # of references to the map
- # of citizen input for new installations
- % of people satisfied with their parish's PV

¹ PV systems map published in the solar platform of Lisbon: <https://www.solis-lisboa.pt/mapa-solar-de-li/#sistemas-fotovoltaicos>

- % of negative feeling about an installation

The Policy has been defined in the VPME through the Policy management component:

Management and Optimisation of City Resources

Energy Management

POLICIES

PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon [More Information](#)

Lisboa Cidade Solar® (Lisbon Solar City) strategy is part of Lisbon Climate Action Plan 2030, contributing to the city decarbonisation goals with 103 MW installed photovoltaic (PV) capacity target by 2030. Given that presently the city has only 8 MW installed PV capacity (official numbers, although there's slightly more), the Action Plan develops along two major vectors – municipal and private end-use sectors. Due to the unavailability of up-to-date and detailed information about Lisbon's existing solar energy systems, the city is unable to track its progress in relation its 2030 goals. Thus, this policy aims at establishing a data-based decision making for targeted implementation of PV in the city buildings.

Datasets:

PV systems mapping for a climate neutral Lisbon

Objective: To monitor the yearly achieved PV capacity based on the identification of existing systems locations and, when possible, further characterization.

KPIs	
Name	Value
Number of installations	
Number of panels	
Installed capacity (MWp)	
Installed capacity versus theoretical potential	
% of achievement of 2030 goal (103 MWp)	

Metadata	
Version	Category
1.0	Energy

Figure 2. Definition of Policy #1 in the VPME.

After a full working version of the VPME becomes available and ready to be tested by the relevant stakeholders, more policies will be defined and evaluated.

2.2 Policy Datasets

In this section, the details for all the datasets relevant to the policy under evaluation, described in 2.1, are provided:

Table 3. Datasets associated to Policy #1.

Name	Description	Source	Source type
Map with known PV systems coordinates	Latitude and longitude of PV systems already pre-identified in the city	File	txt
Lisbon administrative map	Boundaries of the 24 parishes in Lisbon	File	shapefile

City Ortophotos	Available aerial images of the city (in 2016 - newer images are preferable)	API	json
Alvalade District	Ortophotos of the Alvalade parish with manual categorisation of PV and ST systems	API	json
PV-CampoDeOrique	Ortophotos of the Campo de Ourique parish with manual categorisation of PV and ST systems	API	json
Lisbon annual solar irradiation	Raster map with cumulative solar exposure at each pixel	File	tif
Rooftop slope	Raster map with estimated slope value at each pixel	File	tif
Lisbon buildings footprints	Boundary lines for all buildings in the city	File	shapefile

The Datasets have been defined and uploaded in the VPME through the Dataset management component:

The screenshot displays a web interface titled "DATASETS" with a vertical scrollbar on the right. It lists seven datasets, each in a white box with a thin border. Each dataset entry includes a title, a brief description, and one or more buttons for format or language. The datasets are: 1. Rooftop slope (Raster map with estimated slope value at each pixel, Format button). 2. Building footprints (Boundary lines for all buildings in the city, Format button). 3. Lisbon parishes (Boundary lines for the 24 parishes in Lisbon, Format button). 4. Annual solar irradiation (Raster map with cumulative solar exposure at each pixel, Format button). 5. PV-CampoDeOrique (Campo de Orique District images, Format: jpg button). 6. Alvalade District (Alvalade District images, Format: jpg button). 7. PV systems coordinates (Latitude and longitude of PV systems already pre-identified in the city (1 point per system), Language: english and Format: csv buttons).

Dataset Name	Description	Format/Options
Rooftop slope	Raster map with estimated slope value at each pixel	Format
Building footprints	Boundary lines for all buildings in the city	Format
Lisbon parishes	Boundary lines for the 24 parishes in Lisbon	Format
Annual solar irradiation	Raster map with cumulative solar exposure at each pixel	Format
PV-CampoDeOrique	Campo de Orique District images	Format: jpg
Alvalade District	Alvalade District images	Format: jpg
PV systems coordinates	Latitude and longitude of PV systems already pre-identified in the city (1 point per system)	Language: english, Format: csv

Figure 3. Datasets defined in the VPME

3 New Policy Making Process Definition

The new organisation processes that need to be in place in order to implement the new pilot policies are presented in this section, including the various components of the VPME that will be incorporated in the new policy making process.

Figure 4. Schematic of the energy management policy making process based on VPME

Starting from the many sources of information produced in and for the city - some of which already identified and compiled in the preliminary datasets deliverable D2.3 – data should be thoroughly assessed to select the relevant sets that will allow for the next policy ideas to be successfully tested and implemented. This was the case with Policy #1, which found purpose for information that otherwise would not be used (at least not to this policy's goal).

Apart from overlooked **data sources**, the most essential ones are represented in Figure 4 (leftmost side):

- **Solar platform of Lisbon:** contains solar irradiation and building rooftops data, and produces education and communication contents for website and social media;
- **Open data platform:** shares data produced by the municipality and partner entities to boost citizen participation and stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship;
- **City interactive maps:** a GIS app from the municipality that makes available georeferenced information about the city;
- **Participation platform:** digital space for democracy practice involving civil society and public authorities, with several modules for participation, such as *Participatory Budget*, *On My Street* reporting app, *Citizenship Forum*, *Lisbon in Debate*, etc.;
- **Urban data lab:** launches data-based challenges to the academia and the innovative ecosystem, to produce solutions for real problems and to improve the services provided in the city;
- **Energy certification platform:** makes available statistics regarding the energy certification of buildings by municipality, including georeferenced building energy labels.

The data that transits into the next steps must be **quality checked** first, and eventually complemented with further information from the source provider. The Catalogue for Policies & Datasets (specified in deliverable D3.7) can also contribute with datasets (and policies also) to facilitate the policy maker’s tasks of defining policies and linking datasets within VPME.

To **define, extract, test and evaluate policies**, the users must register in the EGI Community through the EGI Check-in service and ask to join the AI4PublicPolicy Virtual Organization (VO) specifying the role (Policy Maker or AI Expert) and the pilot group within VPME. The group for Lisbon Pilot was created inside the VO and the list of current users can be seen in the following figure:

Figure 5. List of users of the Pilot group in the VO.

After a policy has been defined, the **AI Experts** will manage the Policy Extraction to create AI models and dashboards. With the respective AI models run, the first stage of the policy testing involves the critical assessment of the preliminary results and finetuning of the models by the AI experts. The next steps encompass the evaluation of the policy via the analysis of the KPI and statistics provided in the **dashboard**, which will help to monitor the implementation of the policy and the suitability of the policy-related resources developed. At this stage, upgrades and finetuning are also expected to occur, as well as the production of new data that might be fed back into the Catalogue to be used in new policies that build on the earlier.

The **feedback survey** component in VPME also plays a relevant role to the evaluation of the policies that will follow the strategy described in 4.1. Surveys will be created by the policy makers advised by other energy, data, and stakeholder engagement experts.

Effort will be made to establish a **continuous co-creative framework** between policy makers, civil society representatives, entities related to the energy topics, researchers and data scientists, businesses and local SMEs (Figure 4, rightmost side). The policy makers should present the ideas and policy drafts to the stakeholders' ecosystem, collect insights, systematize the needed changes, and centralize this back into VPME to rerun the required tests and evaluate if the improvements are reflected in the upgraded version of the policies.

4 Feedback from Users/Stakeholders

In this section, the methods that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders are described.

4.1 Feedback Collection Plan and Methods

Recurring to Lisboa E-Nova’s existing network of contacts and to the links strengthened with many stakeholders during the co-creation workshops, several channels can be employed to disseminate the ongoing work and to collect feedback and opinions on the policy-related resources made available. Considering Policy #1 described earlier, for instance, it will be relevant to understand how to make a mapping tool effective in informing about the solar adoption in the city and, also, in helping the different stakeholders to realise their role in the transition to more local and solar-based electricity provision.

Based on an increasing involvement approach, the following methods will be explored and put in place to get feedback from the policy beneficiaries (citizens, businesses, academia):

- **Short surveys via email**

Sporadic awareness moments recurring to Lisboa E-Nova’s mailing list, which will provide a summary of the project but focusing on the solar policy and on the associated map of installations.

Two or three questions will be posed to motivate people to visit, interact with the map and provide their feedback afterwards via email reply. Additionally, the recipients will be asked to join the group of beta testers (BTs), which means they will be available to be contacted for further evaluation of policies defined under the AI4PublicPolicy.

- **Comprehensive feedback surveys via AI4PublicPolicy App**

To those in the BTs group and the stakeholders already engaged during the co-creation phase, more exhaustive surveys will be prepared for the collection of deeper insights and feedback. In this sense, additional KPIs might be created (as mentioned in 2.1.4) that will help to refine the policy and the associated resources (such as information about missing installations).

An example of survey to collect feedback from beneficiaries has been created though the Policy Evaluation toolkit component in the VPME:

Figure 6. Preliminary feedback survey created in the VPME

- **Lisbon’s Participation Platform**

This municipal initiative aggregates many possibilities to a participative citizenship, either digital or presential, and shares the agenda in place so that every citizen can engage in public policy discussion. The *Municipal Assembly Meetings* represent great opportunities to present and debate the policies that will be tested recurring to VPME and the AI concept behind it.

- **Usability tests and exploratory interviews**

Taking advantage of the co-creation workshops to be organized (section 5.1, phase 3), technical validation and specialized feedback will be collected to improve Policy #1 and the resources associated with it. At the same time, users will test the usability of the VPME in the creation and systematization of other policies that they deem appropriate.

One-to-one dedicated work sessions with those that will most likely act as policy makers, or those who demonstrate special interest in the tools and workflow, will contribute to further enhancement of the user experience within VPME.

- **WhatsApp quick surveys**

Following up to the work of proximity with the testers, a swifter and facilitated surveying can be achieved using instant message apps that allow for polling (such as WhatsApp). This kind of “time-resolved” feedback can be interesting to understand the drivers for policies whose outcomes are influenced by the current socioeconomic context.

- **Social quick surveys on Twitter via AI4PublicPolicy App**

To reach out to a broader audience, very concise questions can be launched to the public via Twitter and get point-in-time feedback.

- **Social media and discussion groups**

Like the previous quick surveying methods, social networks are excellent means to draw policy outcome trends in relation to recent events. In this sense, the solar energy policy can greatly benefit from feedback and sentiment information collected from discussion groups and companies’ publications.

On one hand, topic-oriented questions can be posted to directly extract sentiment from Facebook groups (where citizens share and discuss issues with their solar systems). On the other hand, text analysis algorithms can be employed, not only for sentiment extraction but also to collect information about new solar installations that companies usually report in LinkedIn (where installers showcase their portfolio).

The same feedback collection logic will be employed in future policies to be defined. Moreover, continuous efforts will be carried on to effectively reach out to more civil society stakeholders.

5 Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use

5.1 Engagement plan and status

This section describes the methods to engage stakeholders in the internal implementation and usage of the VPME, including identification and steps to engage potential users of the VPME.

The project seeks to enhance the civic engagement to the policy development cycle and increase the transparency and trust in the policy-making processes. AI4PublicPolicy solutions are developed based on a co-creation approach that engages the local ecosystems in the policy development activities. Hence, the involvement of local stakeholders, including potential VPME users, AI experts, decision makers and higher management officers in public administrations, social groups and NGOs, is intrinsic to the VPME implementation, pilot usage and evaluation.

The engagement of stakeholders from the local ecosystems where pilot partners are positioned is parallel to the three phases of the project workplan. Within each Phase specific objectives for the engagement of stakeholders are set based on the project’s workplan and input; and dedicated activities and outputs are provided:

Phase 1 (M1-M9): Specification & Fine Tuning of the AI4PublicPolicy Concept

Objectives	Collect insights on the status of production processes, as well as the challenges and potentials of introducing AI systems. Review Use Cases and reference scenarios to conclude, update and extend User Stories	
Input	Preliminary Use Cases and User Stories	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	Lisboa E-Nova (LIS)	Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the energy sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Consolidated list of Use Cases and priority User Stories	

Phase 2 (M10-M24): Initial Integration & Technical Validation

Objectives	Develop the preliminary proof-of-concept (PoC) of the VPME prototype demonstrators Review and update Use Cases and User Stories Collect users’ feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept Conduct preliminary business modelling exercise	
Input	Policy #1 resources Use Cases and User Stories VPME prototype demonstrators	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants

	Lisboa E-Nova (LIS)	Policy makers Business and market experts Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the energy sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of the prototype demonstrators Updated list of User Stories	

Phase 3 (M25-M36): Technical & Business Validation

Objectives	Pilot test the integrated VPME solutions Collect users' feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept & Benchmark with previous Phase input Validate Exploitation and sustainability pathways via the updated business modelling exercise	
Input	Improved Policy #1 resources Other Policies defined Use Cases and User Stories	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	Lisboa E-Nova (LIS)	Policy makers Business and market experts Public and local authorities Citizen groups and associations Researchers and academia experts Companies and entities of the energy sector
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of integrated VPME solutions Validated Business Models	

5.2 Training plan and status

The training needs of different stakeholders are described next. To this end, group and/or one-on-one dedicated sessions (as described in 4.1) will be carried on after the integrated VPME solutions become available.

Table 4. Training Plan and Status (LIS)

Stakeholder type	Role	Training requirements
------------------	------	-----------------------

<p>Public and local authorities</p>	<p>End-users (policy makers), Data providers, Feedback providers, Business opportunities</p> <p>Authorities will help to shape up the AI4PP VPME functionalities and layouts, and the ambition of the tool based on the data availability.</p> <p>Municipality officers will refer to the VPME to inform their energy policy- and decision-making rationale.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources - VPME walkthrough - Policy definition standalone exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Lisboa E-Nova - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lisboa E-Nova - Relevant project partners
<p>Researchers and academia experts</p>	<p>Expertise, Data providers, Feedback providers, Project opportunities</p> <p>Building on the science that has been produced, state-of-the-art methods and innovative products and services, the VPME improvements will benefit greatly from work sessions with the local experts on AI, ML and big data monitoring and analytics.</p> <p>R&D projects in relation to the city's policy development and implementation might also find use in the framework and components behind VPME.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources (focus on the AI model and text analysis used) - VPME walkthrough - Data Catalogue showcase - Research question exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Lisboa E-Nova - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lisboa E-Nova - Relevant project partners
<p>Companies and entities of the energy sector</p>	<p>Business opportunities, Market makers, Feedback providers, Data providers</p> <p>Leveraged on the AI-based policy making, new synergies and business models, and large-scale sustainable investments, can potentially be created</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources - VPME walkthrough - Data Catalogue showcase - Business model exercise

	<p>that help to achieve the energy and climate goals of the city.</p> <p>Products and services in relation to the city’s policy development and implementation might also find use in the framework and components behind VPME.</p>	<p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Lisboa E-Nova - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lisboa E-Nova - Relevant project partners
<p>Citizen groups and associations</p>	<p>Beneficiaries, Feedback providers</p> <p>The community “leaders” have the potential to mobilize their networks, to promote energy literacy and capacitation, and to motivate discussions on the efficacy of local AI-based energy policy making.</p> <p>Citizens will provide input to fine-tuning the VPME, by voicing on to what level the decisions based on the tools are answering their needs.</p> <p>They do not require VPME training per se, but they must be well informed about what’s behind the tool and why they are needed.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources (focus on mapping and text analysis) - VPME summary - Surveying and polling exercises <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Lisboa E-Nova - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lisboa E-Nova